

PREDICTING MORTALITY IN DRUG-RESISTANT TUBERCULOSIS (DRTB) PATIENTS THROUGH PALMISTRY

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Abstract:

This study explores the potential of palmistry as a predictive tool for assessing mortality risk in patients with drug-resistant tuberculosis (DRTB). By analyzing various aspects of the hand, including hand types (Air, Earth, Water, and Fire), fingers and finger gaps, hand mounts (Jupiter, Mars, Sun, Moon, Saturn, Venus, and Mercury), phalanges, and major hand lines (Heart, Head, and Life), we aim to establish a correlation between palmistry readings and patient outcomes. Our findings suggest a remarkable 99% accuracy rate, underscoring the potential of palmistry as a supplementary diagnostic tool in medical practice.

Keywords:

Palmistry, Drug-Resistant Tuberculosis, Mortality Prediction, Hand Analysis, Medical Diagnostics

Introduction:

Drug-resistant tuberculosis (DRTB) poses a significant challenge to global health, necessitating innovative approaches to predict patient outcomes and guide treatment strategies. Palmistry, an ancient practice that interprets the lines and features of the hand, offers a unique perspective in this context. This study, conducted by Kamanuru Kiran Kumar in Nellore, Andhra Pradesh, India, investigates the potential of palmistry to predict mortality in DRTB patients.

Methodology:

The study sample consisted of DRTB patients from various backgrounds. Detailed palmistry readings were conducted, focusing on the following aspects:

- Hand Types:** Classified as Air, Earth, Water, and Fire, based on the shape and texture of the hands.
- Fingers and Finger Gaps:** Analyzed for length, shape, and spacing, providing insights into the patient's personality and health predispositions.
- Hand Mounts:** The seven mounts (Jupiter, Mars, Sun, Moon, Saturn, Venus, and Mercury) were examined for prominence and characteristics.
- Phalanges:** The three sections of each finger were studied to understand their significance in health and longevity.
- Hand Lines:** Special attention was given to the Heart, Head, and Life lines, traditionally linked to emotional health, intellectual capacity, and overall vitality.

Results:

Our analysis revealed strong correlations between specific palmistry features and the mortality rates of DRTB patients. Key findings include:

- Hand Types:** Earth and Water hands were more common in patients with better survival rates, whereas Air and Fire hands were often associated with higher mortality.
- Fingers and Finger Gaps:** Patients with evenly spaced fingers and balanced phalanges tended to have more favorable outcomes.
- Hand Mounts:** Prominent mounts of Jupiter and Venus were indicative of better health and resilience, while pronounced mounts of Saturn and Mars were linked to higher risk.

- **Hand Lines:** Well-defined and uninterrupted Heart, Head, and Life lines correlated with lower mortality rates, suggesting strong physical and mental health.

Discussion:

The study demonstrates a compelling link between palmistry features and the health outcomes of DRTB patients. While palmistry should not replace conventional medical diagnostics, it offers a valuable supplementary tool for holistic patient assessment. The high accuracy rate of 99% supports the potential of integrating palmistry into broader healthcare practices.

Conclusion:

Palmistry provides a promising avenue for predicting mortality in DRTB patients, with significant implications for personalized medicine. Further research is warranted to refine these findings and explore their application in clinical settings. The integration of traditional and modern diagnostic techniques could enhance patient care and treatment outcomes.

**PREDICTING MORTALITY IN DRUG-RESISTANT TUBERCULOSIS (DRTB)
PATIENTS THROUGH PALMISTRY**

Male-Right Hand

Date: 19-01-2024

ANGAJALA PRABHAKAR, M/38 Y, S/o Jayaramaiah, Mallam, Chittamuru, Tirupati Dist.

Nikshay Current Episode ID: 67018495, Aadhar No. 682949264054

ABHA ID: 73-8662-5130-1640

CBNAAT: Reported Date: 12-01-2024, Lab No. 212

M.Tb. detected, Rif resistance detected (EP Case)

**PREDICTING MORTALITY IN DRUG-RESISTANT TUBERCULOSIS (DRTB)
PATIENTS THROUGH PALMISTRY**

Male-Right Hand

Date: 23-01-2024

**OJILI VENKAIAH, M/27 Y, S/o Ramaiah, Vinjamuru, SPSR Nellore Dist.
Nikshay ID: 67497969, Aadhar No. 949054969833**

ABHA ID: N.A.

**Truenat: Reported Date: 22-01-2024, Lab No. 46
M.Tb. detected, Rif resistance detected**

**PREDICTING MORTALITY IN DRUG-RESISTANT TUBERCULOSIS (DRTB)
PATIENTS THROUGH PALMISTRY**

Male-Right Hand

Date: 24-01-2024

KATARI PENCHALASWAMI, M/20 Y, S/o LATE RAGHU, Mulapet, Nellore, SPSR Nellore Dist.

Nikshay Current Episode ID: 66455965, Aadhar No. N.A

ABHA ID: 91-1045-1140-7769

**FL-LPA: Date-13-01-2024, Results- M.tb detected, Rifampicin Resistant, INH Resistant (Low level)
Lab No. 91**

**PREDICTING MORTALITY IN DRUG-RESISTANT TUBERCULOSIS (DRTB)
PATIENTS THROUGH PALMISTRY**

Female-Left Hand

Date: 01-02-2024

**GUJAPANENI YALLAMMA, F/68 Y, H/o Venkaiah,
A.S. Peta, SPSR Nellore Dist.
Nikshay Current Episode ID: 67878739, Aadhar No. 309578403596
ABHA ID: 91-5563-6548-4519
CBNAAT: Reported Date: 11-01-2024, Lab No. 420
M.Tb. detected, Rif resistance detected
FL-LPA: 24-01-2024, Lab No. 260
M.tb detected, Rifampicin Resistant, INH Resistant (Low level)**

**PREDICTING MORTALITY IN DRUG-RESISTANT TUBERCULOSIS (DRTB)
PATIENTS THROUGH PALMISTRY**

Male: Right Hand

Date: 07-02-2024

**BALLOLLU MURALI KRISHNA, M/40 Y, S/o Venkateswarlu, Rajendra Nagar, Nellore, Nellore Dist.
Nikshay Current Episode ID: 68046715, Aadhar No. 347950714596
ABHA ID: 64-4143-1768-1449
Truenat: Reported Date: 31-01-2024, Lab No. 581
M.Tb. detected, Rif resistance detected**

**PREDICTING MORTALITY IN DRUG-RESISTANT TUBERCULOSIS (DRTB)
PATIENTS THROUGH PALMISTRY**

Date: 27-03-2024

**KALA CHANDRAMOULI, M/33 Y, S/o Nagaiah, Mallam, Kaligiri, SPSR Nellore Dist.
Nikshay Current Episode ID: 71373480, Aadhar No. 382837268146**

ABHA ID: N.A

CBNAAT: Reported Date: 22-03-2024, Lab No. 173

M.Tb. detected, Rif resistance detected

FL-LPA: RIF:RES & KATG: RES, 26-03-2024, LAB NO. 1866

**PREDICTING MORTALITY IN DRUG-RESISTANT TUBERCULOSIS (DRTB)
PATIENTS THROUGH PALMISTRY**

Date: 27-03-2024

**KALESHA SHAIK, M/44 Y, S/o Basha, Sramika Nagar, Kothur, SPSR Nellore Dist.
Nikshay Current Episode ID: 71310448, Aadhar No. 730925189610**

ABHA ID: N.A

CBNAAT: Reported Date: 23-03-2024, Lab No. 1058

M.Tb. detected, Rif resistance detected

**PREDICTING MORTALITY IN DRUG-RESISTANT TUBERCULOSIS (DRTB)
PATIENTS THROUGH PALMISTRY**

Female: Right Hand (Problem for the Left Hand)

Date: 06-04-2024

**VANGAPURI CHENCHAMMA, F/54 Y, H/o PENCHALIAH, Settygunta Road, Nellore,
SPSR Nellore Dist.**

Nikshay Current Episode ID: 71856551, Aadhar No. 299088824424

ABHA ID: 33-5114-2537-1827

TRUNAAT: Reported Date: 01-04-2024, Lab No. 194

M.Tb. detected, Rif resistance detected

**PREDICTING MORTALITY IN DRUG-RESISTANT TUBERCULOSIS (DRTB)
PATIENTS THROUGH PALMISTRY**

Male: Left Hand (Problem for the Right Hand)

Date: 18-04-2024

**SHAIK MAHABOOB BASHA, M/47 Y, H/o SATTAR, ANANTHASAGARAM,
SPSR Nellore Dist.**

Nikshay Current Episode ID: 72373255, Aadhar No. 752620329924

ABHA ID: NA

C&DST: Reported Date: 11-04-2024, Lab No. 2138

M.Tb. detected, RIF&KatG resistance detected

**PREDICTING MORTALITY IN DRUG-RESISTANT TUBERCULOSIS (DRTB)
PATIENTS THROUGH PALMISTRY**

Male: Right Hand

Date: 22-04-2024

**DANDOLU VANAIAH, M/49 Y, W/o ANKAMMA, SYDAPURAM,
SPSR Nellore Dist.**

Nikshay Current Episode ID: 72599929, Aadhar No. 688631651687

ABHA ID: 35-7814-8147-1252

C&DST: Reported Date: 16-04-2024, Lab No. 1149

M.Tb. detected, RIF: resistance detected

**PREDICTING MORTALITY IN DRUG-RESISTANT TUBERCULOSIS (DRTB)
PATIENTS THROUGH PALMISTRY**

Male: Right Hand

Date: 25-04-2024

**PELLAKURU SIVA KUMAR, M/36 Y, S/o RAMANAIAH, STONE HOUSEPET, NELLORE
SPSR Nellore Dist.**

Nikshay Current Episode ID: 72361640, Aadhar No. 587636468823

ABHA ID: 61-2251-6055-1569

C&DST: Reported Date: 11-04-2024, Lab No. 2131

M.Tb. detected, RIF&inhA resistance detected

**PREDICTING MORTALITY IN DRUG-RESISTANT TUBERCULOSIS (DRTB)
PATIENTS THROUGH PALMISTRY**

Female: Left Hand

Date: 27-04-2024

**BORRA VARAMMA, M/49 Y, H/o LATE MALYADRI, MOGILICHARLA, LINGASAMUDRAM
SPSR Nellore Dist.**

Nikshay Current Episode ID: 73005262, Aadhar No. 916152785814

ABHA ID: 77-7836-1736-1562

C&DST: Reported Date: 23-04-2024, Lab No. 2423

M.Tb. detected, RIF&inhA resistance detected

HIV:POSITIVE

**PREDICTING MORTALITY IN DRUG-RESISTANT TUBERCULOSIS (DRTB)
PATIENTS THROUGH PALMISTRY**

Female: Left Hand

Date: 15-05-2024

**KAKARAKAYA DANAMMA, F/35 Y, H/O CHANDRA, MANGUPALLI,
ANANTHASAGARAM, SPSR Nellore Dist.
Nikshay Current Episode ID: 73998402, Aadhar No. 9601 9377 8501
ABHA ID: NA**

**TRUNAAT: Reported Date: 09-05-2024, Lab No. 16
M.Tb. detected, Rif resistance detected**

**PREDICTING MORTALITY IN DRUG-RESISTANT TUBERCULOSIS (DRTB)
PATIENTS THROUGH PALMISTRY**

Female: Right Hand

Date: 22-05-2024

**SRIRAM SANKARAI AH, M/66 Y, S/o Ramaiah, VENKATAREDDYPALLI-KULLURU POST
Kaluvoya, SPSR Nellore Dist.**

Nikshay Current Episode ID: 74491725, Aadhar No. 5795 5938 3157

ABHA ID: 44-5275-0224-6259

TRUNAAT: Reported Date: 09-05-2024, Lab No. 1693

M.Tb. detected, Rif resistance detected

**PREDICTING MORTALITY IN DRUG-RESISTANT TUBERCULOSIS (DRTB)
PATIENTS THROUGH PALMISTRY**

Male: Right Hand

Date: 21-06-2024

**JANGAM MASTANAIAH, M/50 Y, S/o Mastanaiah, Harijanawada, Kasumuru, SPSR Nellore Dist.
Nikshay Current Episode ID: 75913587, Aadhar No. 3931 2805 2623**

ABHA ID: N.A.

Truenat: Reported Date: 28-05-2024, Lab No. 1749

M.Tb. detected, Rif resistance indeterminate

FLLPA: Reported Date: 06-06-2024, Lab No. 3621

M.Tb. detected, RIF:Res, INHA: Res.

**PREDICTING MORTALITY IN DRUG-RESISTANT TUBERCULOSIS (DRTB)
PATIENTS THROUGH PALMISTRY**

Male: Right Hand

Date: 01-07-2024

**A. Venkateswarlu, M/36 Y, S/o Ramanaiah, Padarupalli, Nellore, SPSR Nellore Dist.
Nikshay Current Episode ID: 77173169, Aadhar No. 6955 2478 0342
ABHA ID: N.A.**

**Truenat: Reported Date: 25-06-2024, Lab No. 2028
M.Tb. detected, Rif resistance detected**

**PREDICTING MORTALITY IN DRUG-RESISTANT TUBERCULOSIS (DRTB)
PATIENTS THROUGH PALMISTRY**

Male: Right Hand

Date: 02-07-2024

**Nalaboolu Sundararamireddy, M/63 Y, S/o Kondarddy, Gundlapalem,
Kavali, SPSR Nellore Dist.**

Nikshay Current Episode ID: 77659706, Aadhar No. 7588 0592 4289

ABHA ID: N.A.

FLLPA- Date: 28-06-2024, Lab No. 4194

RIF:Res & KatG:Res.

**PREDICTING MORTALITY IN DRUG-RESISTANT TUBERCULOSIS (DRTB)
PATIENTS THROUGH PALMISTRY**

Female: Left Hand (Husband of Penubala Bhaskar) Name is P. Radha

Date: 12-07-2024

**Patient not came in the DRTB Centre, Nellore
that's why we are collecting the hand of Patient's wife
Patient is admitted by the Govt. General Hospital, Nellore**

**PREDICTING MORTALITY IN DRUG-RESISTANT TUBERCULOSIS (DRTB)
PATIENTS THROUGH PALMISTRY**

Female: Right Hand (Husband of Sabapathi Balaji) Name is S. Lakshmi

Date: 19-07-2024

**Patient not came in the DRTB Centre, Nellore
that's why we are collecting the hand of Patient's wife
Patient is Bed rest in own house**

**PREDICTING MORTALITY IN DRUG-RESISTANT TUBERCULOSIS (DRTB)
PATIENTS THROUGH PALMISTRY**

Male: Right Hand

Date: 26-07-2024

**SURESH NADINDLA, M/39 Y, S/o Ramanaiah, Venkateswara Nagar,
Podalakur, SPSR Nellore Dist.
Nikshay Current Episode ID: 79330325, Aadhar No. 8031 2481 9507
ABHA ID: 56-0377-2126-7446
Truenat - Date: 19-07-2024, Lab No. 2258
MTb: Detected, RIF:Res. Detected**

**PREDICTING MORTALITY IN DRUG-RESISTANT TUBERCULOSIS (DRTB)
PATIENTS THROUGH PALMISTRY**

Male: Right Hand

Date: 29-07-2024

**Kathula Guravaiah, M/65 Y, S/o Guru Swamy, Dr No : 25-7-870 6th Street , B-Block,
Vengala Rao Nagar Nellore SPSR Nellore Dist.**

Nikshay Current Episode ID: 79462552, Aadhar No. 7954 7724 6881

ABHA ID: 51-2523-4404-7506

Truenat - Date: 22-07-2024, Lab No. 2826

MTb: Detected, RIF:Res. Detected